

PUBLICATIONS RELATING TO FORESTRY IN NEPAL

Abstracts and titles from
journals in the FRIC Library

Policy, etc.

(87/1) MAHAT, T.B.S.; GRIFFIN, D.M.; SHEPHERD, K.R. Human impact on some forests of the middle hills of Nepal. 1. Forestry in the context of the traditional resources of the state. Mountain Research and Development (1986) 6 (3) 223-232.

This part deals with Nepal as a whole. Parts 2 and 3 will concentrate on Sindhupalchok and Kabhre Palanchok Districts and Part 4 on the area around Thokarpa village, to the east of the Sun Kosi river. Part 1 is derived from secondary sources on the history, etc. of Nepal, extracting and synthesizing information relevant to forestry. It is shown that deforestation and forest degradation have their origins in the systems of land tenure, taxation and forced labour (exacted as piece work, e.g. as the supply of prescribed quantities of firewood) that go back to the beginning of the Nepali state in the eighteenth century. There was virtually no legislation or administrative action to conserve the forests until the reforms of 1950. The government's intentions have been frustrated in many ways since then, but the authors conclude that recent legislation allowing forest land to be allocated to the panchayats 'has sown the seeds of effective community forestry'.

Keywords: Policy; history; deforestation.

Statistics

(87/2) ASHBINDU SINGH. The national forest cover monitoring using satellite imagery. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (6) 477-484.

Discusses the lack of reliable statistics on forest cover in India and the possibility of using LANDSAT or similar data. The difficulties of interpretation in steep terrain are emphasized.

Keywords: remote sensing; deforestation.

(87/3) BROWN, A; WOLF, L. New tree crop database. ACIAR Forestry Newsletter No. 2, Sept./Oct. 1986, p. 2.

Describes TREDAT, a database for plantation trials. It requires supermicro or mini computers: 'such as Microvax or Vax'.

Keywords: data processing.

Community forestry

(87/4) WILSON, J. Management of community forests in Tamil Nadu. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (4) 305-313.

In the 1960s and 1970s, 133 000 ha of community lands (6.2 % of the area of the State) were planted, mainly with Acacia nilotica and some A. leucophloea on the banks of minor irrigation 'tanks'. The State Forest Department manages them and gives 50% of the revenue to the panchayats. This income has been put to good use for building schools and community halls, water and sanitation schemes, roads, etc. Since there is little shortage of firewood in rural Tamil Nadu, much of the produce has been sold in urban areas. Revised management systems will aim at more direct benefits to the villagers, such as timber supplies, grazing and fodder.

Keywords: Acacia nilotica; Acacia leucophloea; community forestry.

(87/5) MAITHANI, G.P.; MISRA, N.M.; MAHENDRA, A.K. Socio-economic factors associated with fuel consumption in rural areas (vill. Karaundi). Indian Forester (1986) 112 (9) 753-761.

Keywords: fuelwood; sociology.

Agroforestry

(87/6) WHITEMAN, P.C.; OKA, G.M.; MARMIN, S.; CHAND, S.; GUTTERIDGE, R.C. Studies on the germination, growth and winter survival of Gliricidia maculata in south-eastern Queensland. International Tree Crops Journal (1986) 3 (4) pp. 245-255.

Keywords: Gliricidia maculata; fodder; agroforestry.

(Agroforestry, continued)

(87/7) O'KTING'ATI, A.; MONGI, H.O. Agroforestry and the small farmer: a case study of Kilema and Kirua Vunjo in Kilimanjaro [Tanzania]. International Tree Crops Journal (1986) 3 (4) 257-265.

Keyword: agroforestry.

(87/8) YAMOA, C.F.; AY, P. The use of Gliricidia sepium for alley cropping in the southern Guinea savanna zone of Nigeria. International Tree Crops Journal (1986) 3 (4) 267-279.

Keywords: Gliricidia sepium; agroforestry.

Erosion control

(87/9) SONI, P.; AVATAR SINGH; VASISTHA, H.B.; MATHUR, H.N. Prototype hydroseeder developed at FRI [Research Note]. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (4) 366-368.

A description, with a diagram, of a locally made device costing IR 500, that was designed for seeding mine spoil near Dehra Dun and has been successfully tested on slopes of 70 degrees.

Keywords: tools and equipment; erosion control; direct sowing.

Soils

(87/10) JORGENSEN, J.R.; WELLS, C.G. Tree nutrition and fast-growing plantations in developing countries. International Tree Crops Journal (1986) 3 (4) 225-244.

Discusses published data on nutrient removal by Pinus oocarpa, Eucalyptus spp., and Leucaena leucocephala; nutrient sources for fast-growing plantations; and nutrient balances, with theoretical balance sheets for potassium and nitrogen for Eucalyptus and Leucaena. It is concluded that with high production, intensive plantation management that does not use biological N-fixation or nitrogen and other fertilizers, tree growth will decline to a level that can be sustained by natural nutrient-cycling processes. On some sites it may be best to use management practices other than intensive plantation forestry.

Keywords: Pinus oocarpa; Eucalyptus; Leucaena leucocephala; nutrient cycle; nitrogen fixation.

(87/11) SINGHAL, R.M.; SONI, S. Comparative study of the bio-chemical composition of the plant materials in the Mussoorie Himalayan soils (U.P.). Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 264-270

In chir (Pinus roxburghii), oak (Quercus incana) and deodar (Cedrus deodara) forests.

Keywords: Pinus roxburghii; Quercus incana; Cedrus deodara; soil chemistry.

(87/12) SINGHAL, R.M.; SONI, S. Measurement of hexoses in acid hydrolysates of some soils of Mussoorie Himalayas. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (4) 342-352.

Under Cedrus deodara, Pinus roxburghii and Quercus incana respectively.

Keywords: Cedrus deodara; Pinus roxburghii; Quercus incana; soil chemistry.

Ecology

(87/13) SHUKLA, R.P.; RAMAKRISHNAN, P.S. Architecture and growth strategies of tropical trees in relation to successful status. Journal of Ecology (1986) 74 (1) 33-46.

Compares early-successional and late-successional trees in northeast India.

Keywords: succession; tree architecture; rain forest.

(87/14) SINGHAL, R.M.; RAWAT, V.R.S.; PRAMOD KUMAR; SHARMA, S.D.; SINGH, H.B. Vegetation analysis of woody species of some forests of Chakrata Himalayas - India. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (9) 819-832.

In 12 sites representing different forest types [for species see Keywords].

Keywords: Cedrus deodara; Pinus roxburghii; Picea smithiana; Pinus wallichiana; Quercus floribunda; Quercus semicarpifolia [semecarpifolia]; Quercus leucotrichophora; Abies pindrow; Rhododendron arboreum; Lyonia ovalifolia; vegetation types.

(87/15) KHAN, M.L.; RAI, J.P.N.; TRIPATHI, R.S. Regeneration and survival of tree seedlings and sprouts in tropical deciduous and sub-tropical forests of Meghalaya, India. Forest Ecology and Management (1986) 14 (4) 293-304.

Regeneration was studied in relation to light conditions, ground vegetation and soils in three ecologically different forests at Upper Shillong, Mawphlang and Burnihat. The dominant trees include several genera and species that are also found in Nepal.

Keywords: natural regeneration; ecology.

Pines

(87/16) DADWAL, V.S.; JAMALUDDIN; SONI, K.K. Uptake, translocation and persistence of benlate and bavistin in Pinus caribaea seedlings. Indian Journal of Forestry (1986) 9 (2) 123-125.

These were tried as general systematic fungicides. Both had phytotoxic effects at 0.1 and 0.2 % concentrations. Bavistin at 0.05 % gave the best results and is recommended for further trial.

Keywords: Pinus caribaea; fungicide.

(87/17) BHARTARI, S.K. Biological productivity and nutrient cycling in Pinus patula plantations of Darjeeling hills. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 187-201.

Sample trees were taken to represent the average tree in plots aged 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 years. Estimates were made of total biomass and by tree components and the results are tabulated. Concentrations of N, P, K, Ca and Mg were estimated in the aerial parts and in the litter. From the results it is suggested that in fast-growing species like P. patula a high proportion of the nutrient uptake is retained in the tree.

Keywords: Pinus patula; nutrient cycle.

(87/18) EVANS, J. Productivity of second and third rotations of pine in the Usutu Forest, Swaziland. Commonwealth Forestry Review (1986) 65 (3) 205-214.

A report of studies on Pinus patula, P. taeda and P. elliottii. The only evidence of declining productivity is on one site where the soil is low in phosphate. In some cases productivity has increased, possibly because of the use of better seed. A discussion of similar studies in Australia notes that where declining yields have been confirmed it has been possible to take effective measures, including the use of fertilizers.

Keywords: Pinus patula; Pinus taeda; Pinus elliottii; increment; fertilizers; soil chemistry.

Spruce

(87/19) OMBIR SINGH; SHARMA, K.C.; CHAUKIYAL, S.P.; SHARMA, S.K. Time of trans-planting spruce seedlings. Indian Journal of Forestry (1986) 9 (2) 137-139.

In a nursery at Shillaru, Himachal Pradesh, at 2400 m, seed of Picea smithiana was sown on 7 April (1981). The best time for transplanting the seedlings into beds was found to be the first fortnight of August.

Keywords: Picea smithiana; nursery management.

Bamboos

(87/20) NATH, M.; PHUKAN, U.; BARUA, G.; DEVI, M.; BARUA, B.; DEKA, P.C. Propagation of certain bamboo species from chemically treated culm cuttings. Indian Journal of Forestry (1986) 9 (2) 151-156.

Internodal cavities of culm cuttings were filled with IAA, NAA, GA3, boric acid and Kinetin in various concentrations, separately and in various combinations, and the cuttings planted horizontally. Best induction of shoots and roots was obtained, for Bambusa balcooa, B. vulgaris and Dendrocalamus hamiltonii, with IAA + Kinetin; and for B. pellida and Teinostachyum dullooa with NAA + Kinetin.

Keywords: Bambusa balcooa; Bambusa vulgaris; Bambusa pellida; Dendrocalamus hamiltonii; Teinostachyum dullooa; vegetative propagation; growth regulators.

(Bamboos, continued)

(87/21) FARID UDDIN AHMED; SHARMILA DAS. Flowering in Bambusa vulgaris Schrad. [Research Note]. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 275-276.

A report of flowering in one clump in Kutubdia, Bangladesh. No seed was produced. This is in accordance with previous reports about this species. It is suggested that the cause of no seed setting may be sterility of the pollen or its failure to produce a pollen tube.

Keywords; Bambusa vulgaris; flowering.

(87/22) SHARMA, O.P. Mass multiplication of Dendrocalamus hamiltonii Munro - a critical evaluation. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (6) 517-523.

In Himal Pradesh, where offsets for using in the 'traditional' method are in short supply. Author's summary:

'Performance of one-node culm cuttings with preformed roots at (i) primary-branch bases, and (ii) culm nodes was evaluated. They were taken from under one-year-old juvenile (actively branched) and adult culms respectively and planted in March. In the first case, out of 391 cuttings 323 survived, of which 301 produced complete plants, ready for out-planting, in one year. In a particular culm the cuttings that died belong to the distal region in a basipetal order. The new plant starts from a branch. In the second case, out of 603 cuttings only 104 produced complete plants in the first year. The number rose to 309 in the second year, but the remaining 294 cuttings died or ended blindly. The new plant starts from a bud.'

Keywords: Dendrocalamus hamiltonii; vegetative propagation.

Eucalyptus

(87/23) FLORENCE, R.G. Cultural problems of Eucalyptus as exotics. Commonwealth Forestry Review (1986) 65 (2) 141-163.

A discussion, based on a wide review of the literature (75 refs.) and consultation with other staff of the Australian National University and the

Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organization, of the possible undesirable environmental consequences of planting eucalypts. The main conclusions are:

- The range of genetic material available has not been adequately tapped in introduction programmes.

- With care, eucalypts can produce wood at a lower nutrient cost than many other fast-growing species.

- Some observed effects on soils may be due to competition rather than a 'toxic influence'.

- High wood production will be matched by high water use but 'whether the water use efficiency declines to any appreciable degree under some environmental conditions cannot be determined from the available evidence'.

- 'In drier regions, particularly, it may be necessary to determine the eucalypt species and patterns of land use which will best meet the objectives of land management and avoid undue social conflict'.

Keywords: Eucalyptus; forest influences; hydrology; soil.

(87/24) HETH, D; FANGER-VEXLER, L; REUVENI, O. Mass production of cuttings of Eucalyptus camaldulensis Dehn. Commonwealth Forestry Review (1986) 65 (3) 215-225.

'Semi-commercial' production of rooted cuttings in Israel has been effected by first producing stockplants, either by coppicing selected adult trees and rooting cuttings taken from coppice shoots, or by grafting adult shoots onto seedlings to produce (a few) cuttings that can be rooted to make stockplants. The initial take of grafts was highly successful, but survival fell to 15% after one year; some cuttings can be taken before the graft fails. It is estimated that ten thousand stockplants per ha can produce a million cuttings per year, half of which will produce rooted plants.

Keywords: Eucalyptus camaldulensis; vegetative propagation.

(87/25) SINGH, A.K.; BHATTACHARYA, A.K.; KAMLA SINGH; DIWEDI, B.N. Evaluation of essential oil in Eucalyptus varieties grown in Kumaon hills (Ranikhet), Uttar Pradesh for timber. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 223-228.

Data are presented for quantity and main constituents of oil from samples

(Eucalypts, continued)

of 14 species [see Keywords], and for the effects of open storage of the leaves before distilling.

Keywords: Eucalyptus robertsonii; Eucalyptus rubida; Eucalyptus globulus; Eucalyptus goniocalyx; Eucalyptus darrympleana; Eucalyptus laevopinea; Eucalyptus microcorys; Eucalyptus camaldulensis; Eucalyptus regnans; Eucalyptus viminalis; Eucalyptus grandis; Eucalyptus amygdaline; Eucalyptus racemosa; Eucalyptus saligna; essential oils.

(87/26) DAYAL, R.; AYYAR, K.S. Sub L [?] Eucalyptus globulus sub sp. bicostata leaves - a new source of medicinal oil [Letter to the Editor]. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 277.

Samples gave 6.58% essential oil with more than 70.5% cineole, compared with subsp. globulus in the Nilgiris which has a max. of 1.25% oil with 62% cineole. Plantations of subsp. bicostata are recommended.

Keywords: Eucalyptus globulus; essential oils.

(87/27) BANERJEE, B.; NANDI, A.; NATH, S.; BANERJEE, S.K. Characteristics of the soils supporting quality class I Eucalyptus tereticornis in south Bengal. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (9) 762-772.

Keywords: Eucalyptus tereticornis; soil types.

(87/28) CHANDRA, J.P.; YADAVA, M.P.S. Clonal propagation of Mysore gum (Eucalyptus hybrid). Indian Forester (1986) 112 (9) 783-791.

In trials in the Bagwala Research Nursery, Rudrapur (Nainital) on Mysore gum [Eucalyptus tereticornis], budding, grafting, air-layering and softwood cuttings gave 40, 83, 18 and 45 % success respectively. Treatment with IBA at 10 000 p.p.m. was beneficial for air-layering and cuttings.

Keywords: Eucalyptus tereticornis; clones; vegetative propagation.

(87/29) KAPUR, S.K.; GUPTA, B.N. Recovery of scantlings from Eucalyptus logs. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (6) 491-501.

Eucalyptus 'hybrid' [E. tereticornis] in the Punjab, mainly for pallets.

Keywords: Eucalyptus tereticornis; sawmilling; pallets.

Sal

(87/30) SANJIVA RAO, V.; MADHUSUDHAN RAO, K. Detanning of deoiled sal (Shorea robusta) seed meal with sodium carbonate followed by washing with water. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 253-260.

Laboratory trials showed that tannin content can be reduced from 18.3% to less than the desired maximum of 4%. The optimum results were obtained with an alkali concentration of 0.015 kg/litre and a water-to-cake ratio of 47 litres/kg.

Keywords: Shorea robusta; minor forest products; fodder.

Daphne

(87/31) JEANRENAUD, J.P.; THOMPSON, I. Daphne (lokta), bark biomass production: management implications for paper making in Nepal. Commonwealth Forestry Review (1986) 65 (2) 117-130.

Nepal foresters are familiar with the background to this article, the production of 'lokta' hand-made paper, and the need to manage the forest resources on which this cottage industry is based. Details are given of the latest studies on bark production and the desirability of longer rotations; for single trees productivity per annum rises rapidly as the rotation increases to twenty years or more, but it is accepted that a realistic prescription is for a minimum rotation of 10 yr, corresponding to a breast-height diameter of 3.0 cm. Three possible management systems are discussed, based on cutting by area, by diameter limit, or a combination of the two. The second option is proposed as being the most realistic for the present. It is stressed that what is really needed is integrated conservation and management of the whole stands in which Daphne spp. form the understorey.

Keywords: Daphne; forest management; small-scale forest industries.

Leucaena

(87/32) PATHAK, P.S. Fuel and forage production from Leucaena leucocephala under farm forestry. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (6) 485-490.

A 5-year rotation had a greater m.a.i. than a 4-year one. A second rotation gave double the production of the first. Tabulated data are presented.

Keywords: Leucaena leucocephala; fodder; fuelwood.

Poplar

(87/33) RAIZADA, A; SRIVASTAVA, M.M. Litter production in a Populus deltoides Marsh. plantation.

At Dehra Dun.

Keywords: Populus deltoides; biomass litter.

Casuarina

(87/34) REDDELL, P.W. Management of nitrogen fixation by casuarina. ACIAR Forestry Newsletter No. 2, Sept./Oct. 1986, pp. 1,3.

Research at the CSIRO Division of Soils, Adelaide, has shown that not all Frankia spp. nodulate all casuarinas, and that the effectiveness of different Frankia spp. varies on different Casuarina spp. Soil P content has a marked effect on nodulation and N fixation. Casuarina spp., which are faster growing, need more P than Allocasuarina. Probably, small applications of P would allow Casuarina to be grown on soils that naturally only support Allocasuarina. Nodulation (in C. cunninghamiana) has been shown to be affected by temperature; at [and below?] 15°C it was poor. Work continues. The Division of Soils is maintaining a bank of Frankia strains.

Keywords: Casuarina; Allocasuarina; Frankia; nitrogen fixation; root nodules; soil chemistry.

Other broadleaves

(87/35) SAGWAL, S.S. Pre-sowing treatment of puna (Ehretia acuminata) seed. Indian Forester (1986) 112 (3) 261-263.

Control (no treatment) gave 49.6%, scarification gave 73.2%, putting in

boiling water and allowing to soak while cooling for 24 h gave 66.0%, and treatment with conc. sulphuric acid gave 87.6% germination.

Keywords: Ehretia acuminata; seed germination.

Book review

LANDON, J.R. (ed.). Booker tropical manual. Booker Agricultural International Ltd. & Longman, Harlow, UK., 1984. 450 pp.

This manual is a compilation of information designed for those involved in soil survey and land evaluation. However, it does not require an advanced understanding of soil science, and as a comprehensive soil reference book it will be of value to research workers, students, teachers - and even foresters! It is a concise and easy-to-use handbook in which soil-related methods and terminology are summarized and demystified in a readable style. The main text is aimed more at the non-specialist, with emphasis on the practical applications of soil survey, and contains clear guidelines for the interpretation of soil and land-evaluation data. The Annexes list methods and provide checklists and worked examples that are all of particular value to the soil specialist, but other readers will find the tabulated weights and measures conversions, the glossary, and the climatic classification very useful. Despite its title, the usefulness of the manual is not restricted to the tropics. Although some of the guidelines and examples are designed for developing countries within the tropics and subtropics, most of the information presented can be used by people working with natural resources in most environments. J. Teare.

Keywords: soil surveys; land use.

Notice

JACKSON, J.K. Manual of afforestation in Nepal.

This book is now available from the Forest Research and Information Centre. The price to purchasers is £25 (including postage). Cheques should be made payable to 'FRP Publications'. We hope to publish an independent review of this important work in our next issue.

New journal

New Forests ['an international journal biology, biotechnology, and management of afforestation and reforestation']. Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, Dordrecht, Boston, Lancaster. Quarterly. \$32 (individuals); \$72 (institutions). ISSN 0169-4286.

We have received Vol. 1, No. 1 (1986) as a sample of this journal. It contains four articles, a review paper and a research note. With the possible exception of the last (DONG, H; BURDETT, A.N. Chemical root pruning of Chinese pine seedlings raised in cupric sulfide impregnated paper containers) they seem to be of little direct relevance to forestry in Nepal.

Keyword: publications.

New manuals

K.J White, Plantation Consultant, Sagarnath Forest Development Project, has produced a series of six manuals relating to this major industrial forestry plantation project in the terai. We hope to publish reviews of them in our next issue. Their titles are:

- Manual No. 1. Intercrop strategies and practices in the bhabar terai of central Nepal.

- Manual No. 2. Tree farming practices in the bhabar terai of central Nepal.

- Manual No. 3. Forest nursery strategies and practices in the bhabar terai of central Nepal.

- Manual No. 4. Forest fire control strategies and practices in the bhabar terai of central Nepal.

- Manual No. 5. Practical tree breeding strategies and practices and

programmes in the bhabar terai of central Nepal.

- Manual No. 6. Organisation and management practices for the Sagarnath Project of central Nepal.

Keywords: publications; agroforestry; plantations; nursery management; fire control; tree breeding; forest management.

New series

The HMG-USAID-GTZ-IDRC-Ford-Winrock Project, Strengthening Institutional Capacity in the Food and Agricultural Sector in Nepal, is publishing a Forestry Research Paper Series, edited by M.B. Wallace. The first seven titles (all dated December 1986) are:

- Number 1. GAUTAM, K.H. Private planting: forestry practices outside the forest by rural people.

- Number 2. DEVKOTA, G.P. A viable alternative energy for rural Nepalese villages: a case study of Gobar gas.

- Number 3. SILWAL, U.K. Attitude, awareness, and levels of people's participation in the community forestry development program, Nepal.

- Number 4. PAUDYAL, K.R. Noncommercial cooking energy in urban areas of Nepal.

- Number 5. UPRETY, L.P. Fodder situation: an ecological-anthropological study of Machhegaon, Nepal.

- Number 6. SHARMA, R.K. Nonformal forest development cooperatives: a case study of Bhokraha village, Nepal.

- Number 7. JOSHEE, B.R. Improved stoves in minimization of fuelwood consumption in Nepal.

Keywords: publications; community forestry; sociology; fodder; cooperatives; stoves; energy.

Titles from other bibliographic sources

Note: These titles, selected as being of general interest, can be followed up by consulting the abstracts or by obtaining the original document. The keywords are provided by Banko Janakari. This issue contains titles from Forestry Abstracts (FA) and Forest Products Abstracts (FPA). FA 47 and FPA 9 are the 1986 volumes. In future issues we hope to include selections from other 'secondary sources'.

FA 47/3243 GUNN, C.R. Fruits and seeds of genera in the subfamily Mimosoidaceae (Fabaceae) [Mimosaceae]. Technical Bulletin, USDA (1984) No. 1681.

Keywords: Mimosaceae; seed; taxonomy.

FA 47/3257 PHUKAN, M.K.; MITRA, G.C. In vitro regeneration of Albizia [Albizia] odoratissima Benth., a shade tree for the tea plantation of north-east India. Two and a Bud (1983) 30 (1/2) 54-58.

Keywords: Albizia odoratissima; tissue culture.

FA 47/3438 SHARMA, E.; AMBASHT, R.S.; SINGH, M.P. Chemical soil properties under five age series of Alnus nepalensis plantations in the Eastern Himalayas. Plant and Soil (1985) 84 (1) 105-113.

Keywords: Alnus nepalensis; soil chemistry.

FA 47/3495 RAJVANSHI, R; GUPTA, S.R. Mineral cycling in a tropical deciduous Dalbergia sissoo Roxb. forest. Acta Oecologica, Oecologica Plantarum (1985) 6 (3) 247-262.

Keywords: Dalbergia sissoo; soil chemistry; nutrient cycle.

FA 47/3568 EGUILUZ-PIEDRA, T.; ZOBEL, B.J. Geographic variation in wood properties of Pinus tecunumanii. Wood and Fiber Science (1968) 18 (1) 68-75.

Keywords: Pinus tecunumanii; wood properties; provenance.

FA 47/3815 VIEGAS, P.; MENON, G. The social costs of deforestation. Social Action (1985) 35 (4) 326-350.

Keywords: sociology; deforestation.

FA 47/3820 REDDY, S.T.S. Who prefers eucalyptus and why. Social Action (1985) 35 (4) 366-378.

Keywords: Eucalyptus; sociology.

FA 47/3878 VANDANA SHIVA; BANDYOPADHYAY, J.; JAYAL, N.D. Afforestation in India: problems and strategies. Ambio (1985) 14 (4/5) 329-333.

Keywords: afforestation; policy.

FA 47/3891 FOLEY, G. Wood fuel and conventional fuel demands in the developing world. Ambio (1985) 14 (4/5) 253-258.

Keywords: energy; fuelwood.

FA 47/4104 BACHELARD, E.P. Effects of soil moisture stress on the growth of seedlings of three eucalypt species. I. Seed germination. Australian Forest Research (1985) 15 (2) 103-114.

Keywords: Eucalyptus; soil water; seed germination.

FA 47/4188 BAJRACHARYA, D.; BHATTARAI, T.B.; DHAKAL, M.R.; MANDAL, T.N.; SHARMA, M.R. SITAULA, S.; VIMAL, B.K. Some feed values for fodder plants from Nepal. Angewandte Botanik (1985) 59 (5/6) 357-365.

Keyword: fodder.

FA 47/4273 SHARMA, E.; AMBASHT, R.S. Seasonal variation in nitrogen fixation by root nodules of Alnus nepalensis plantations in the eastern Himalayas. Journal of Applied Ecology (1984) 21 (1) 265-270.

Keywords: Alnus nepalensis; nitrogen fixation.

FA 47/4445 REPETTO, R. World enough and time. Successful strategies for resource management. New Haven, USA. Yale University Press (1986) xiv + 147 pp.

Keywords: natural resources; policy.

FA 47/4455 INDIA, SOCIETY OF TROPICAL FOREST SCIENTISTS. Journal of Tropical Forestry (New journal).

Keyword: publications.

FA 47/4456 POORE, [M.E.]D. (Ed.) (INDEPENDENT COMMISSION ON HUMANITARIAN ISSUES) The vanishing forest. The human consequences of deforestation. London. Zed Books Ltd. (1986) 89 pp.

Keywords: deforestation; sociology.

FA 47/4464 SIREN, G.; MITCHELL, C.P. (Eds.). Forest energy and the fuelwood crisis. Proceedings of the IUFRO Project Group P1.09.00 meeting in Uppsala, Sweden, June 8-9, 1984. Rapport, Avdelingen for Energiskogsodling, Sveriges Landbruksuniversitet (1985) No.41, vi + 138 pp. [Individual papers are also noticed in FA/FPA, but not here].

Keywords: energy; fuelwood; conference.

FA 47/4486 TEMU, A.B.; WEAVER, G.H. Forestry, domestic energy and environment in Tanzania. Resource Management and Optimization (1986) 3 (4) 319-325.

Keywords: energy; fuelwood; environment.

FA 47/4500 CHAKRAVATI, R. Some observations on fuelwood forestry in India. Journal of Tropical Forestry (1985) 1 (1) 3-17.

Keyword: fuelwood.

FA 47/4505 SIDDIQUI, K.M.; REHMAN, S.; HUSSAIN, A. Suitability of Eucalyptus kitsoniana for planting in Pakistan. Pakistan Journal of Forestry (1985) 35 (4) 175-180.

Keywords: Eucalyptus kitsoniana.

FA 47/4511 BABELEY, G.S.; KANDYA, A.K. Effect of various pretreatments on germination and vigour of Leucaena leucocephala Lam. de Wit. seeds. Journal of Tropical Forestry (1985) 1 (1) 85-90.

Keywords: Leucaena leucocephala; seed germination.

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